

Solar filament detection, classification, and tracking with deep learning

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This study introduces a comprehensive deep learning framework for the detection, classification, segmentation, and tracking of solar filaments using H α images from the Global Oscillation Network Group (GONG) data archive. Solar filaments, phenomena in the solar corona, are of significant scientific interest due to their link with violent eruptive events such as coronal mass ejections. Using together a DETR-based model for detection and classification, a U-Net for instance segmentation, and a custom-made tracking algorithm, we achieved state of the art performance across all tasks, overcoming typical challenges. The proposed methodology significantly advances solar filament analysis, offering improved capabilities for automated studies and potential applications in space weather prediction.

1 Introduction

The Sun is a constant source of activity, including flares, coronal mass ejections (CMEs) or solar energetic particles (SEPs). CMEs are the main drivers of the most severe space weather disturbances. They are vast amounts of magnetized plasma ejected from the Sun which propagate into the interplanetary space, often leading to geomagnetic storms when they encounter Earth [1–6]. The origin of CME formation and other eruptive events lies in the Sun's complex magnetic activities, frequently in regions of intense activity [3, 4]. Our understanding of CMEs origin is still developing, but it is known that solar filament eruptions are strongly correlated with CMEs and flares [7–10].

Solar filaments, also known as prominences, are large scale structures of cooler and denser plasma suspended in the solar corona by magnetic field lines [3, 11–16]. They are best observed in the H α spectral line (6562.8 Å) as dark stripe-like shapes on the solar disk, or bright loops in the limb when observed against the dark space sky (see Figure 1).

Filaments can be classified into three types by their location respect to an active region [11, 17]: quiescent

region filaments (QRF), intermediate region filaments (IRF), and active region filaments (ARF).

Several research efforts have focused on automating the detection of solar filaments. Initially, works like [13, 18] relied on setting intensity thresholds on H α images, which is problematic due to the resemblance in brightness levels with other phenomena like sunspots, as well as variations across instruments and observing conditions. Recently, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have popularized, demonstrating improved performance. Ahmadzadeh et al. [15] developed a filament segmentation model, however they only did binary segmentation and failed to achieve sufficient accuracy, impacted by their reliance on threshold-based labeling methods. Other studies [16, 19, 20] developed detection and segmentation models, but only addressed binary detection, or merely classified filaments as isolated or non-isolated.

The latest work by Zheng et al. [21] shows good progress with a combined detection and tracking algorithm that employs a U-Net [22] for segmentation and CRST algorithm [23] for tracking. Despite its general success, this algorithm struggles with fragmented filaments, and is challenged with small filaments due to reliance on threshold-based labeling. Moreover, they do not classify filaments, only binary segmentation.

This research aims to address these limitations by adopting a different methodology that encompasses detection, classification, segmentation, and tracking of solar filaments, employing deep learning (DL) techniques.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Data

This work employs full-disk H α solar observations from the Global Oscillation Network Group (GONG) data archive [24]. GONG is a network of several telescopes worldwide, capturing images of the Sun in near real-time since 2010, which come pre-processed to re-

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Figure 1: Example of a preprocessed full disk $H\alpha$ image from GONG, with some active region filaments (ARF), intermediate region filaments (IRF), quiescent region filaments (QRF), and sunspots classified for reference. A filament seen in the limb is also marked. The image was taken from El Teide observatory in Spain at 2023-11-29, 11:49 UTC.

move typical issues present in astronomical images. Despite this, certain factors such as exposure, limb darkening, and other interferences (bad weather conditions, blurriness, trees, etc.) might still degrade the effectiveness for filament identification.

In this regard, we corrected exposure employing histogram equalization inside the solar disk and re-scaling intensities outside the disk with the help of some routines from the python packages `scikit-image` [25] and `sunpy` [26]. Additionally, limb darkening was corrected by normalizing the solar image's radial intensity profile.

2.1.1 Data labeling and filament classification

To train a DL model for detecting and classifying filaments, we produced a labeled dataset using the open-source Labelme tool [27]. We randomly selected and downloaded a set of GONG $H\alpha$ images from April 2010 to December 2023, and preprocessed them for exposure and limb darkening effects, discarding images with the presence of clouds, blurriness, etc. After that, the dataset was carefully labeled by hand.

Manual labeling involved an expert visualizing each $H\alpha$ image to identify and annotate filaments, classifying them into three types: QRF, IRF, and ARF [17]. Filaments observed outside the solar disk were not taken into account. The final labeled set consists of 554 images, including 2258 QRFs, 570 IRFs, and

512 ARFs. We also labeled all sunspots to help the model differentiate between them and filaments. The dataset contains 804 sunspots.

Unlike threshold-based detection, which uses a pre-defined brightness threshold to identify filament pixels, manual labeling allows for more accurate differentiation of filaments from other dark structures like sunspots, noise, etc. Threshold methods can easily confuse filaments with these elements due to similar brightness levels. Varying observational conditions and differences between telescope cameras can cause brightness levels to vary significantly between observatories. Additionally, thresholding can miss ARFs, which are often less dark due to their bright surroundings, and small filaments are also easy to miss. Manual labeling incorporates expert knowledge, ensuring the dataset reflects true physical structures, which is essential for effectively training DL models.

2.2 Models

2.2.1 Detection and classification

To detect and classify filaments, we used a pre-trained DETR model [28] on the ImageNet dataset.

To adapt this model to our dataset, we resized images to 800×800 pixels, normalized them using mean 0.453 and standard deviation 0.338, and applied the following data augmentation techniques: random rotations ($0 - 364^\circ$), horizontal and vertical flips, and random sharpening (sharpness factor 0-31). Images were also randomly cropped to the solar disk size.

Using both raw and processed images, we trained the model with Adam optimizer [29] and a cyclical learning rate schedule [30] between 10^{-4} and 10^{-5} , over 85% of the dataset.

2.2.2 Image segmentation

To obtain filament segmentation masks, we trained a separate U-Net [22] on each labeled filament.

We cropped labeled filaments from their original solar images using the detected bounding boxes coordinates, then normalized them with the same mean and standard deviation as before, and resized them to 256×256 pixels.

We trained the U-Net from scratch using Adam optimizer and a combination of constant learning rates (10^{-4}) and cyclic schedules (10^{-4} to 10^{-7}). The resulting segmentation masks were transformed back to their original sizes for individual analysis.

2.2.3 Sequence generation

Continuous and arbitrary long sequences of $H\alpha$ solar images are necessary for tracking purposes. Therefore,

we downloaded images from different GONG observatories around the globe, merging them sequentially, taking a time interval of 1 hour between subsequent frames.

At this point, disturbances such as bad weather, blurriness, etc. affect a substantial percentage of the images, detrimentally impacting tracker efficiency. To address this issue, we downloaded a random set of images from 2010 to 2024 and manually labeled them as good (normal) or bad (cloudy, blurry, ...). This resulted in a final set of 1821 good images and 751 bad images. After that, we trained on this set a simple CNN consisting of two convolutional layers with maxpooling [31] and ReLU [32] activations. We used this model as a filter to download clean sequences.

2.2.4 Tracking model

Tracking filaments over time is challenging due to their dynamic nature. They move slowly on the solar surface but can rapidly change shape, fragment, merge, or disappear. Furthermore, ground-based observation is complicated for continuous tracking, as it requires multiple instruments worldwide, each one with different settings, and potentially affected by disturbances like bad weather. Therefore, simple and common tracking methods fail.

We developed a custom system that assigns track IDs based on overlapping intersection over union (IoU) values from the DETR model detections, along with image similarities from histograms and local binary patterns. Furthermore, we applied a Kalman filter [33] to track bounding box positions.

The full tracker algorithm follows these steps: (1) Initialize the tracker with detections from the DETR model. (2) For subsequent frames, detect filaments with the DETR model and update the tracker with the aforementioned algorithm. (3) Remove filaments from tracking if undetected for four consecutive frames.

3 Results

This section presents a concise summary of the results obtained through the analysis of the GONG H α images dataset.

On the one hand, the DETR-based detection and classification model was evaluated using standard metrics—average precision (AP), average recall (AR), and F1 score—adopting different IoU detection thresholds. The evaluation was performed on a test set made with 15% of the total set.

On the other hand, the U-Net segmentation model was evaluated with mean IoU and Dice-Sørensen sim-

ilarity coefficient between predicted masks and annotated ground truth masks from the test set.

Finally, the tracking algorithm was evaluated with the multiple object tracking accuracy (MOTA) metric [34] over a continuous 3-day period, using an IoU overlapping threshold of 0.5 for detections. This metric was computed for all filaments, irrespective of their type.

Table 1 presents the evaluation metrics results of all models and Figure 2 shows some examples of the models' performance.

Model	Metric	QRF	IRF	ARF	Overall
DETR	AP_{50}	0.95	0.97	0.95	0.95
	AP_{75}	0.77	0.87	0.77	0.78
	$AP_{50:95}$	0.67	0.72	0.67	0.67
	AR_{50}	0.96	0.97	0.96	0.97
	$AR_{50:95}$	0.74	0.80	0.73	0.74
	$F1_{50}$	0.95	0.97	0.95	0.96
	$F1_{50:95}$	0.69	0.75	0.70	0.70
U-Net	IoU	0.82	0.78	0.80	0.81
	Dice	0.90	0.87	0.89	0.89
Tracker	MOTA				0.82

Table 1: Performance metrics for the detection, classification, segmentation, and tracking algorithms over the test dataset. For the DETR-based model, average precision (AP), average recall (AR), and F1 scores are shown. For the U-Net, the intersection over union (IoU) and Dice coefficient are used. The tracker algorithm is evaluated with the multiple object tracking accuracy (MOTA) metric. Metrics are provided for individual classes of quiescent region filaments (QRF), intermediate region filaments (IRF), and active region filaments (ARF), as well as overall performance for all classes.

4 Discussion

4.1 Comparison with previous studies

The proposed DL models of this work have shown good performance across all studied tasks of detection, classification, segmentation, and tracking of solar filaments.

First, the DETR-based detection and classification model achieved high precision, recall, and F1 scores across all filament types. Previous studies [15, 16, 21] reported values of AP_{50} , AR_{50} , and $F1_{50}$ up to 0.91, 0.82, and 0.87, respectively. In all cases, the DETR-based model showed stronger performance.

Secondly, the U-Net model also performed well. For

the task of filament segmentation, previous studies [15, 21] reported IoU values up to 0.67, and [20] obtained a mean Dice coefficient of 0.89. In comparison, our U-Net model achieved equal or better results.

Lastly, the tracking algorithm demonstrated strong performance as well, achieving a high MOTA value of 0.82, comparable to the average tracking accuracy value of 81.7% reported by Zheng et al. [21].

4.2 Strengths and limitations

The DETR-based model showed excellent performance, making it well-suited to automate the study of filament properties. However, it is important to note that the whole dataset is relatively small due to the labor-intensive process of manual labeling. Moreover, this work is based solely on GONG data. Future work should focus on training and testing the model on different and larger datasets to improve and ensure its generalizability.

On the other hand, the improvement in our U-Net model’s filament segmentation capabilities can be attributed to using individual filaments instead of full-disk solar images. This approach naturally increased the training data size, as the samples are the number of filaments rather than the number of solar images. Moreover, it allows to retain the original image resolution of the filaments, which would otherwise be severely reduced when resizing full-disk solar images to fit into GPU memory, specially affecting small filaments. Shortcomings of this approach, however, are slower processing times and potential misses if the DETR model fails to detect some filaments before applying segmentation. This could be fixed by designing more efficient processing pipelines and/or quantize the models.

The tracking algorithm performed well, accurately tracking the majority of filaments over several days, even when faced with obstructions like clouds or abrupt changes in brightness and contrast levels. However, it struggles when filaments fragment or merge. This issue could be mitigated by incorporating distance thresholds, utilizing U-Net segmentations for similarity, or developing an additional DL model to identify similarities between sequential filaments. Furthermore, poor observing conditions over extended periods can hinder the system. Implementing cloud-cleaner algorithms, such as the one proposed by Feng et al. [35], or using space-based telescopes like CHASE [36] could overcome this problem.

Figure 2: Some examples showing the performance of the models. (a)-(d) are pair of images showing the DETR-based model detection and classification capabilities. Left images—(a) and (c)—correspond with ground truth labeled samples, while right images—(b) and (d)—are the DETR-based model’s detection bounding boxes and classifications. (e)-(j) are pair of image croppings showing the U-Net model segmentation capabilities. Left (blue) images correspond with the ground truth segmentation masks, and right (red) images are the U-Net’s segmentation masks.

5 Conclusions

This study presents a complete DL approach for the detection, classification, segmentation, and tracking of solar filaments using $H\alpha$ images from the GONG data archive. Several DL models were developed to solve each problem, reaching state of the art performance in all of the tasks. Though tested on a limited dataset, our methodology highlights significant advancements in solar filament analysis, providing a

foundation for further refinement and broader data application in predicting space weather phenomena.

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